

Structuring a course based on the global engineer

Vitória Bento Botelho¹, Octavio Mattasoglio Neto², João de Sá Brasil Lima¹

¹ Mauá Institute of Technology, Brazil. Mechanical Engineering Program. São Caetano do Sul, SP, Brasil.

² Mauá Institute of Technology, Brazil. Teaching Academy. São Caetano do Sul, SP, Brasil.

Email: vivi.bbotelho@gmail.com, omattasoglio@maua.br,joão.brasil@maua.br

Abstract

This article presents a proposal for the implementation of the Grand Challenges Scholars Program (GCSP), created by the National Academy of Engineering, in an engineering teaching institution in Brazil. The GCSP focuses on teaching by soft skills and shows great intersection with the soft skills of Curricular Guidelines for engineering programs in Brazil. Besides this relation, it is clear that the use of active strategies for learning is a point of encounter between these two strategies and, in particular, the use of projects and PBL, can be the inducer for learning these strategies. The GCSP aims to build soft skills in their participating students by placing them in the face of major problems. This work involves the elaboration of a possible way of implementing the GCSP in an educational institution and, as a reference, the construction of a project in the area of Mechanical Engineering. The GCSP requires customization, hence each student receives individual guidance from a tutor who will shape the student's path to optimize his performance in the program. The implementation of this new teaching approach becomes important, since, currently, the freshmen in university programs, in most cases, do not arrive with the experience in the job market that students of the past used to have. In that way, only the technical part of the academic training is not enough for the professional development of the student who is inserted in an increasingly competitive job market, requiring flexible and versatile engineers, capable of proposing solutions to the most diverse problems. The work is based on document analysis method and an recorded interview with a key person to implement this proposal.

Keywords: GCSP; Teaching by projects; soft skills; global engineer.

1 Introduction

The Pro-Rector of the Maua Institute of Technology (IMT-acronym in portuguese) had the first contact with this project. He participated in a workshop in Brazil, where some schools around the world presented the implementation of the Grand Challenges Scholars Program (GCSP) in their curriculum. It was when he realized an important alignment with the IMT. The Pro-Rector shared his thoughts about the GCSP with Professor Joseph Yossif, who has been in touch with the curators of the program since 2019 as the IMT found this opportunity important to add value to the institution.

This work aims to propose a way of implementing the GCSP in an engineering higher education institution. The GCSP program, an educational supplement created by the National Academy of Engineering, was created with the motivation that institutions became interested in the 14 challenges of the NAE Grand Challenges for Engineering (National Academy of Engineering), to improve the lives of people with engineering solutions in the 21st century. This program encourages the creation of innovative projects in educational institutions that, in order to participate, need to follow five soft skills, presented in item 2.1 in this work, when addressing the chosen objective. These soft skills aim to promote the training of an engineer concerned with global problems.

In this work, the soft skills of the GCSP were raised and analyzed together with the skills required in the National Engineering Curriculum Guidelines, in order to justify the presence of the GCSP in a Brazilian institution and also, to present a possible way of implementation. The importance of this research is due to the need to create a new professional identity that can only be achieved with the effective involvement of the student with global challenges, which requires an involvement and empathy with the problems of the world. This identity seems that can only be accomplish with a path that effectively allows the development of soft skills making this professional sensitive to global problems. The GCSP program can bring this new vision to students and teachers.

2 Literature Review

2.1 Grand Challenges Scholars Program

In 2008, the National Academy of Engineering (NAE) created the NAE Grand Challenges for Engineering, with the aim of presenting an aspirational vision of what engineering needs to offer to all people on the planet in the 21st century. This idea was based on 14 objectives that the NAE raised as necessary to achieve this vision in the 21st century considering its four major areas: sustainability, health, safety and joy of living. Many engineering schools and elementary and high school programs have adopted the NAE Grand Challenges to inspire practical projects for their students through an educational supplement called the Grand Challenges Scholars Program (GCSP). The GCSP points out the following five competencies as essential for students to have the necessary tools to deal with these global challenges:

- I. Talent competence: guided research / creative experience on a topic similar to the Grand Challenge
 - II. Multidisciplinary competence: understanding the multidisciplinary of engineering systems solutions developed through personal engagement
 - III. Viable business / entrepreneurship competence: understanding, preferably developed through experience, of the need for a viable business model for implementing the solution
 - IV. Multicultural competence: understanding different cultures, preferably through multicultural experiences, to ensure cultural acceptance of the proposed engineering solutions
 - V. Competence in Social Consciousness: understanding that engineering solutions must mainly serve people and society, reflecting social awareness
- The GCSP is a supplementary program that focuses on four major areas: health, safety, sustainability and joy of living.

The intention is to add to the training of the engineer and make that engineer have a global view, thus, he can use his knowledge to help the world as a whole and not just his community.

2.2 National Curriculum Guidelines to engineering programs of Brazil

The National Curriculum Guidelines (Diretrizes Curriculares Nacionais- DCNs) originate from the Education Guidelines and Bases Act (The Law on Brazilian Education Guidelines and Bases - LDB), 1996, which states that it is the responsibility of the Union, to establish, in collaboration with the states, the Federal District and the municipalities, competences and guidelines for Early Childhood Education, Elementary Education and High School, which will guide the curricula and their minimum contents, in order to ensure common basic training.

The DCNs deal with the structuring of the engineering course, aligning all engineering institutions to guarantee a good training for the engineer. Therefore, the guidelines need to be more generic and comprehensive to achieve the requirements of all areas of engineering and, also, of any professional choice of the trained engineer.

2.3 Curriculum

The engineering curriculum must be according to the most current recommendations of ABENGE (Brazilian Association of Engineering Education), where the student must be able to develop skills and attitudes based on specific knowledge gain through personal experience. What is sought with this curriculum is to deliver to society professionals with training that enables innovation and entrepreneurship, applying what they have learned in practical matters with technique and creativity.

3 Research Method

The research method chosen to develop this work was the case study as it is exceptionally evaluating the scenario of the GCSP implementation in the IMT. However, in this stage of the study will only be considered the DCNs and the bounding conditions for the implementing phase of the GCSP. This research method is a detailed analysis of an individual case, it uses qualitative data, collected from real events, with the aim of explaining, exploring or describing current phenomena inserted in their own context.

In this research was analysed the documents of GCSP and DCNs to compare and cross the skills that are common and those that are no common in each other. To know how the implementation of GCSP are be considered in the school, was carried out an interview with a key person, responsible to structure the proposal of the GCSP.

As a background of the research, the study of the skills desirable to the engineering students have been carried out, as a complement necessary to discuss these process.

4 Data and Results

4.1 IMT curriculum

IMT has a curriculum composed of the following curricular elements: disciplines (fixed, elective, optional), complementary activities, TCC and mandatory supervised internship. The fixed disciplines presents the minimum set of subjects necessary for the formation of the engineer according to the DCNs. While complementary activities, named PAEs in the IMT curriculum, presents a variety of more than 200 subjects as well as academic activities such as Mauaracing, that designs and builds formula SAE style cars or Enactus that does social work. The student is free to select whichever complementary activities he finds more attractive, so that he can complete the mandatory eighty hours per semester of PAEs. These subjects are offered both within the student's area of study, as well as subjects that contribute to the student's personal development. Within the complementary activities, it is also possible to participate in scientific initiation.

Also, the IMT offers minors certificates for the fifth year student who does one of the sets of optional subjects. The mandatory Internship is a supervised school educational act, developed in the work environment, which aims to prepare for productive work.

The IMT dedicates a week before classes start to receive the freshmen, when dynamics and workshops are prepared for students involving engineering challenges. In 2020, one of the proposed dynamics was the resolution of the GCSP water access challenge, which shows the institution's alignment with the GCSP's values, putting the students in contact with engineering problems aligned with GCSP, since the beginning of the graduation program.

4.2 Mechanical Engineering program

The mechanical engineering program at IMT presents the possibility of specializing students in their area of interest. The program is the only one in IMT divided into cells. The objective of the division into cells is to optimize the efforts of all the professors grouped around a common theme like: I) mechanics of solids; II) energy and fluids; III) design and manufacturing processes; IV) materials and V) automotive engineering. The first cell comprises themes like theory of structures, analytical mechanics, vibrations and finite element methods. The second one, themes like fluid mechanics, thermodynamics, heat transfer, turbo machinery and thermal machines. The third cell, themes like manufacturing processes and project/construction of machines. At last, but not least, the last two ones, comprises, respectively, areas like materials for mechanical construction and vehicular propulsion. It is important to point out that are others subareas that pertain to the cells but were not presented here. According to this structure presented, each cell is responsible for all disciplines related to its theme as also as research projects related to the cell. Within each cell there are several trails that the student can take if he/she wants to specialize in some area or wants to prepare him/herself to work, after the undergraduate, in a specific area. The trails were made by the teachers of each area and are formed by the subjects, PAEs, disciplines (elective, optional) and minors. Their creation was motivated because students used to ask professors about what PAEs and disciplines should they take according to their preferences.

4.3 Structural Elements for the implementation of the GCSP

The GCSP, being a supplementary program, presents several ways of implantation in the IMT, however it must follow some basic norms. First, as it is a personalized program, it will be offered to a few people as it is a program that requires a high commitment from the student but as well as from the teacher, who will need to monitor and evaluate his student individually throughout the program that can begin in the second year and

last until the student's final year. The exact number of participating students will still be studied, depends on the availability of teachers and the interest of the student.

There is a consciousness that a few number of students could be attracted by the specific objectives of the GCSP, however it is accepted that the skills developed in the program could influence other students along the scholar life. But, at the first time, it is not the expected.

For the second point of the implementation of the GCSP will be selected the students who most identify with the program in their first or second year of the course, they must be hardworking, curious and creative thinkers, as well as having the will to use their skills to improve the world. To help in this selection the Talent Academy, which is an area of the IMT that is responsible for assisting students in building their curriculum and preparing for job interviews and the job market in general, will be making the selective process of the students willing to participate.

To accompany each student participating in the program, semi and full time resident's teachers of the IMT must be trained to become GCSP tutors. The few tutors selected to the program must be aligned with its values to pass them on to the students. Each participating will be signed with the tutor who can better help their development in whichever area of interest they eventually chose. Once the student chooses between the four grand areas, sustainability, health, security or joy of living, he should set up the trail, that he will go through in his time in the program with his tutor.

The tutoring is a program that already exists in the school, and was implemented since 2015 when a curricular change was started. The role of this tutor is too act as a mentor, being as reference to the students. The tutor, as implemented, accompanies the students only the first semester of the program, helping them to closer the course, oriented them to choose the PAEs at the first initial stages of the program, and make clear the curriculum. With the GSCP implementation, others features will be need to the teacher that will assume this position, and will be necessary training to help them to perform this new function.

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Each participating will be signed with the tutor who can better help their development in whichever area of interest they eventually chose. Once the student chooses between the four grand areas, sustainability, health, security or joy of living, he should set up the trail, that he will go through in his time in the program with his tutor.

In order to trace this path one must follow a pre-defined trail made by IMT and by the NAE, but it is possible to customize according to needs and interests. This pre-defined trail will be made with the complementary activities of the curriculum of IMT, therefore, the PAES. Also the student will have to develop a project, in the style of a scientific work that involves his chosen grand area. The tutor must also evaluate his student to make sure his developing the soft skills required by the GCSP and to help the student to modify the trail as often as it needs to enhance the performance of the participant. The duration of this program depends on which college it is being implemented, however it should last at least two years.

4.4 Discussion

The DCNS soft skills are concerned with the learning process that is, providing tools for the student to develop the skills and competencies necessary for his professional life as an engineer. The GCSP's competences are focused on training engineers who are concerned with the continuity of life on the planet and the quality of the same.

To be aligned with the GCSP and the DCNs one doesn't have to go different ways, on the contrary, the intersection between these approaches indicates that meeting the DCNs for engineering courses puts schools in a technical condition to meet the GCSP, this is an encouraging factor to participate in the GCSP . However, the GCSP is not just a technical guideline, there is a purpose which is the creation of a professional identity that can only be achieved with the effective involvement of the student with global challenges, which requires

an involvement and empathy with the problems that it seems can only be achieved with a path that effectively allows the development of skills that make this professional sensitive to global problems.

The purpose of this program is to the student develops the five soft skills quoted in item 2.1 so that, in addition to their technical knowledge, it is possible to become a global engineer. The Mechanical Engineering course will have several projects to develop and will be in advantage as it has already different trails that one can choose between the four cells of specialization in the curriculum.

The path of each student in the program is flexible to be shaped, so it is unique to each one. The student will be able to take PAES, both subjects or the academic activities (item 4.1) and also do a scientific initiation about one or more of the forty-one (41) projects that were chosen for being aligned with one or more of the four grand areas of the GCSP. The student will choose between these projects for his research. At this point, there are projects involving biologic flows, wind energy, thermo-magnetic engines, waste treatment and much more.

The expectation is to make the assesment of the students based on how they developed and the outcomes of their participation in the activities mentioned above.

As for the instruments of evaluation is being created a structure that predict the implementation of rubrics, so that the tutors can make an individual assessment of the students and also the elaboration of dynamics in which the students will be evaluated in groups. These elements are based on the creation of a formative assessment that guarantees the student a feedback on the development of their performance. Even in the initial phase, these elements are being prepared by the GSCP implementation team at IMT.

The school recognizes that it already has the elements that can be conjugated for the implementation of the GCSP. However, the effective implementation will give the more conditions to evaluate how the soft skills can be developed and also, how the tutors will evaluate more precisely the students.

5 Conclusion

The objective of this work was to present the initial process of implementation of the GCSP in an engineering school, indicating the challenges related to the alignment of this program with the curricular structure, the selection of the students, the role of the tutor and the evaluation of the students. The purpose of this work is, in addition to bringing elements that are the basis of a scientific analysis of this implementation, to help schools that have this same purpose, to follow this path with less difficulties.

Therefore, the IMT has an advantage to implement the GCSP as it is aligned with the DCNs. Though, it is necessary to study and think carefully about the process to select the students and the tutors. The people who are implementing this program are considering more than numbers, such as grades and years of experience, to select someone to join the program, instead they must look to the individual and humanize it. After all, the goals of the GCSP are to make the world more sustainable, healthy and with more joy of living, in order to the deliver these it is necessary, above all qualities, empathy and humbleness to learn.

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